

STRATEGIES FOR PROTECTING YOUTH AND WOMEN FROM EXTREMISM THROUGH SOCIAL MEDIA: INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCES AND PRACTICES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article examines effective measures and experiences from various countries aimed at protecting young people and women from radicalization and negative influences through social media. The analysis includes platforms such as Uzbekistan's "Girls' Academy" and Germany's "Islam-ist." These programs help to enhance digital literacy, develop critical thinking skills, and enable young individuals to critically assess online information, thereby safeguarding them from the impacts of extremism.

Keywords: social media, radicalization, online safety, extremism, digital literacy, social media.

To develop effective measures for protecting women and youth from extremist ideologies, radicalization, and various negative influences on the internet, experiences from different countries have been studied. For instance:

Girls' Academy — a free learning and development platform in Uzbekistan designed for women of all ages. This platform offers various modules that include health, modern professions, crafts, education, entrepreneurship, psychological, and legal knowledge. The lessons, specialized programs, and materials are aimed at providing knowledge ranging from beginner to professional levels.

The Girls' Academy aims to improve literacy among women in various fields, helping them find their place in society and be active in independent life. After registering, users can access interactive lessons and Q&A modules for learning. By actively participating in this community, women can find supportive networks and acquire new skills.

The **Islam-ist platform** is an online Q&A platform organized by Germany's Violence Prevention Network. Its purpose is to provide clear and understandable answers from an Islamic perspective to questions that Muslim youth may encounter in daily life. The platform is aimed at preventing radicalization by offering accurate information about Islam to dispel negative stereotypes and misconceptions.

Islam-ist maintains regular communication with youth through social media channels like Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok, using various tools to reach a broader audience. Within the platform, sections such as "Islam and Diversity," "Islam and Leisure," and "Islam and Communication" allow young people to learn how Islamic knowledge applies to contemporary life. Information about Islamic wisdom and values is presented in a Q&A format, providing practical answers and advice relevant to the daily lives of young people.

The platform also includes videos explaining Quranic verses and Islamic terms, enabling youth to grasp Islamic knowledge in a simple and understandable way. These videos are designed to align with young people's interests and aim to provide them with accurate information [1].

The **Diamond Program**, implemented by the Netherlands' Intercultural Participation and Integration Fund, is a support initiative aimed at assisting young people aged 12 to 24 in addressing various personal and social challenges. This program provides a safe and inclusive online environment where youth can openly explore and discuss sensitive topics, including gender roles, relationships, personal identity, love, and self-expression. By offering a structured space for these discussions, the Diamond Program encourages young people to express themselves, share experiences, and receive guidance on issues that are often difficult to address in everyday life.

Through facilitated online conversations and interactive sessions, the Diamond Program helps youth develop essential life skills and critical thinking abilities, allowing them to navigate complex social topics confidently. The program's emphasis on open dialogue enables participants to ask questions about privacy, societal expectations, and personal relationships. These discussions empower youth by enhancing their self-awareness, empathy, and respect for others, which are key qualities for positive personal development.

Beyond personal growth, the Diamond Program actively promotes social integration among youth by encouraging interaction between individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds. It aims to break down barriers, foster mutual understanding, and cultivate an appreciation for cultural differences. By bridging gaps between varied perspectives, the program helps young participants recognize and challenge stereotypes and biases, ultimately encouraging a more cohesive and inclusive society.

In addition, the Diamond Program's resources include guided workshops and training sessions that offer practical advice on managing relationships and

understanding the complexities of gender roles in different cultural contexts. These resources provide valuable insights that help youth understand and respect diverse viewpoints while developing a balanced approach to identity and personal values.

The program not only supports individual development but also strengthens community bonds by fostering solidarity and shared learning among participants. By guiding youth toward open-mindedness and tolerance, the Diamond Program plays a crucial role in preparing a generation of informed, compassionate, and culturally aware young people who can contribute positively to society [2].

Life After Hate: Based in the United States, Life After Hate offers support for vulnerable online users, provided by former extremists and psychologists. This organization provides various support services to individuals, including young people and their family members, who are emerging from extremist environments.

Life After Hate's main objective is to prevent radicalization, restore friendly relations within society, and protect young people from negative influences. Through its targeted, informed, and adaptable approach, the platform aids individuals from extremist environments in reintegrating into social life. By promoting the concept of "sisterhood" and creating alternative networks and connections outside extremist circles, Life After Hate encourages positive relationships and social reintegration. Many members are former extremists who are now committed to changing their lives, renouncing radical ideologies, and playing positive roles in society [3].

JUUUPORT is a non-profit organization based in Germany, established in 2010 by the Niedersächsische Landesmedienanstalt (Lower Saxony Media Authority) to provide counseling and support for young people navigating the complexities and risks of the digital world. Now operating as a charitable organization known as JUUUPORT e.V., the initiative aims to create a safe, anonymous space where youth can seek help for challenges they face online.

The organization is committed to offering support on a range of internet-related issues that increasingly affect young users. These include **cyberbullying, hate speech, privacy violations, cyber protection**, and exposure to **extremist content**. JUUUPORT's services are designed to be accessible and confidential, encouraging young people to reach out without fear of judgment or exposure. The organization's counselors are trained to address both the emotional and

practical aspects of these challenges, providing personalized guidance to empower youth in managing online conflicts and building resilience.

One of JUUUPORT's key focuses is on supporting **young women and girls**, who often encounter unique challenges online. The organization recognizes the particular vulnerabilities of these groups, offering them tailored advice and resources to navigate online environments confidently and safely. In addition to direct counseling, JUUUPORT also focuses on preventive education, helping young users develop skills to recognize and respond to harmful content proactively.

JUUUPORT engages with youth on social media platforms like **Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Snapchat, and TikTok**, providing resources, tips, and support through channels that young people are familiar with and use frequently. By establishing a strong online presence, JUUUPORT meets young people where they are, fostering an approachable and relevant connection. This proactive engagement on social media also allows the organization to reach a broader audience, raising awareness about the importance of digital safety and the mental health impacts of cyber challenges.

The organization's funding primarily comes from **various German media authorities and organizations**, ensuring the sustainability of its mission to support youth. Through this backing, JUUUPORT continues to expand its services and maintain high standards of counseling, training its advisors to understand emerging digital trends and threats.

JUUUPORT also offers peer-to-peer support, where young people, trained as advisors, help others navigate online issues. This peer-support model is highly effective, as it enables youth to communicate with advisors who understand their generation's unique challenges and digital habits. This approach fosters a sense of community and trust, as young users find comfort in sharing their experiences with peers who genuinely understand their perspective.

Overall, JUUUPORT plays a crucial role in fostering a safer and more supportive online environment for young people in Germany, equipping them with the tools and confidence to handle digital challenges responsibly and confidently. By focusing on both support and prevention, JUUUPORT not only helps youth manage current online issues but also educates them on maintaining a healthy, secure relationship with technology in the future [4].

Web-constables Program by the Estonian Police and Border Guard is an initiative where police officers serve as online safety representatives. This program includes monitoring cyberspace and managing accounts on social

media platforms. The Web-constables Program actively works to maintain internet safety in the community, combating extremist activities and online threats. Police officers in this program alert users to potential dangers, explain the importance of cyber protection, and assist in gathering information on online crimes.

The program's goal is to strengthen internet safety in the community, ensure the security of users online, and guide social interactions on the internet. As a significant tool in maintaining digital safety, the Web-constables Program plays an active role in countering online extremism [5].

In conclusion, today's youth, especially young girls, have access to essential information and the ability to connect with friends through social media platforms, which have become an integral part of their lives. Social media makes it easy for youth to broaden their worldview, make new friends, and access information on various topics. However, many young people lack the skills to assess the reliability of online information, increasing their susceptibility to misinformation, manipulation, and harmful propaganda.

To prevent women and girls from being influenced by foreign ideas through social media, the following recommendations are proposed:

Digital Literacy and Source Verification Skills: In today's digital world, it is essential for women, especially young girls, to develop skills for evaluating the reliability of online information. Digital literacy programs should be developed to teach youth how to recognize propaganda, misinformation, and extremist content. For example, programs like Ireland's BE MEDIA SMART initiative combine fact-checking tools and databases to help users develop skills in using credible sources. Such programs can be a vital tool in protecting youth from the risk of radicalization [6].

Recognizing Extremist Propaganda: Extremist groups often disseminate propaganda in subtle forms aimed at attracting young women and girls. Therefore, women should develop skills to identify these types of extremist propaganda and recognize suspicious content. Specialized training and educational materials should be created to achieve these goals, enabling youth to develop critical thinking skills to differentiate narratives and evaluate their essence [7].

Implementing Platforms and Tools to Promote Digital Literacy: The introduction of digital tools and online learning programs specifically designed for women and girls can enhance their immunity to misinformation and

manipulation on the internet. These platforms provide information to help navigate various challenges and identify suspicious content.

Supporting Critical Thinking Development: Separate guides, training, and webinars should be organized to develop critical thinking skills. Through these programs, youth will learn to evaluate the reliability of various messages and information by focusing on the source, purpose, and content, thus increasing their resistance to misinformation and helping protect them from harmful content on the internet.

Creating Alternative Social Networks and Safe Support Groups: Establishing safe and effective support groups for women will help them maintain healthy relationships on social networks. Such groups play a significant role in uniting young people and distancing them from the influence of extremism. Positive connections and a supportive environment help protect them from negative influences.

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